

Study of Education to Inculcate the Empowering, Imagination and Shaping of the Mind

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Abstract

Education is the biggest powerful tool to deal in all aspect developed abilities, career, guidance, direction. Education important role play in every individual personal life. Education develop the holistic development, creativity, ability, interest in individual life. Education to include the empowering,imagination and to develop the shaping of mind. Education provide the knowledge,skills,to develop character building.Education is very crucial part to develop the social, physical, emotianol etc. Education receive in different aspects fomal, non-foraml and informal education. Eduaction receive structured and unstructured way. Empowerment in education refers to the process of enabling the learning experiences.to develop skills, knowledge, critical thinking to become a more independent. Imagination is a powerful to become imagination thoughts, ideas, conceptuality, abstract thinking through cognitive development.

Keywords: Importance of Education, Rabindranath Tagore, Aurbindo Ghosh, Imagination, Shaping of the Mind

Introduction

Education refers to the continuous process acquiring knowledge, learning and meaning acquiring information.Education divided into categories,formal,informal and non-formal education.education means to develop the holistic development like physical,social,emotial moral,ethics ,brotherhood etc.Education to provide the knowledge skills, creativity and problem solving decision making.education is a life long process.Education transfer one generation to next generation across the culture.The highest education is that which does not merely give us information but makes our life harmony with all existence.By Rabindranation Tagore.Education is not attaining by thinking what you are what you become by Aurbindo Ghosh.

Educational thought of Rabindranath Tagore

It given by tapovan concept by Rabindranath Tagore Education to provide in Mother tongue as a medium language in rural areas.

Education to provide in urban areas in a English medium.

“Rabindranath Tagore says” to development the sense, intellect, emotions among children senses are: eyes, ears, nose, tongue, skin.

- Education provide should by nature.
- Education provide by natural growth in natural circumstances.
- Education provide to develop the holistic development of children.
- Rabindranath Tagore believe that idealism,naturalism etc.
- Curriculum should be activity-based curriculum.
- To develop the Physical development.

- To develop the moral and spiritual development.
- To develop the harmonious development.
- Education must be child-centered education.
- To develop the logical-thinking in children
- To develop the self-awareness.
- To provide the freedom of learner to get learning.
- Education should be provide mental freedom in childs.
- To develop the spiritual development to achieve the educational aims and objectives of education.
- Rabindranath tagore against the rote memorization of learning,bookish knowledge etc.
- Teaching methods given by Rabindranath Tagore
- Teaching method should be Debate and discussion method.
- Teaching method should be Activity method.
- Teaching method should be used Problem-solving method in Teaching method.

“Quote by Rabindranath Tagore (Freedom from Heart, Freedom from Intellect, Freedom for will)”.

Awards of Rabindranath Tagore

Gitanjali, Kabuliwala, Naukadubi, Sons of the Morning.

Holistic Development

Educational Thought of Aurbindo Ghosh

Aurobindo Ghosh, also known as Sri Aurobindo, was a prominent Indian nationalist, philosopher, yoga and poet.

Educational thought emphasizes the holistic development of individuals, not focus only on intellectual growth but also on physical, emotional, and spiritual development.

- To develop self-realization in children.
 - To develop the innate powers among individuals.
 - To develop the morality in Individuals .
 - To develop senses training.
- Five core concept to develop education in individuals:
1. Physical Education
 2. Mental Education
 3. Vital Education
 4. Psychic Education
 5. Spiritual Education

1. **Physical Education:** A healthy and strong body provides the necessary support for intellectual practices. Physical education is necessary for the harmonious development of the body, mind, and spirit.

Health & Fitness, Balance and coordination, strength, vitality, flexibility.

Methods and Practices

Exercise and Sports: Regular physical exercise, including activities like running, swimming, and gymnastics, is important.

Yoga and Asanas: Yoga plays a significant role in physical education through by Aurobindo's philosophy. Practicing asanas (yoga postures) enhances flexibility, strength etc.

2. **Mental Education:** Mental education aims to develop the intellectual abilities, including reasoning, critical thinking, abstract thinking problem-solving, decision-making, analysis, and synthesis.
3. **Vital Education:** The vital education is characterized by emotions, desires, and impulses. It drives our actions and responses in life, often influencing our decisions and behavior. Vital education is essential because the proper development of the vital being contributes to emotional balance, self-awareness, and social harmony.
4. **Psychic Education:** It fosters a deeper connection with one's inner self, leading to self-discovery, spiritual growth, and fulfillment.
5. **Spiritual Education:** Spiritual education is a form of education that aims to develop the divine potential of children and adults.

Empowerment of Education in Students

Knowledge Acquisition: Education helps students to adopt knowledge and information, acquiring knowledge to understand the world around them, to make decisions, and engage critically with information.

Critical Thinking Skills : Education to develop problem solving, decision Making, Creativity, Enhancing Potential Retention, Critical Thinking, Imagination in students to analyze information and problem solving develop reasoned opinions to solve problem Confidence and Self-Esteem:

Self-confidence to improve the self- esteem, love, knowledge, skills, values, morality. Acquiring knowledge and mastering skills through education boosts students' confidence and self-esteem. It gives them a sense of accomplishment and belief in their abilities to overcome challenges.

Shaping of the Mind:

The mind is what we think, feel, perceive information, imagine, remembering power of information and wills, encompassing the totality based on mental phenomena. Mind includes both conscious processes and unconscious processes through which an individual is aware of external and internal circumstances.

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MIND |
|---|--|
| BRAIN is physical organ of the body.
BRAIN has shape & size.
BRAIN has weight.
BRAIN can be touched.
BRAIN is hardware. | MIND is metaphysical.
MIND has no shape & size.
MIND is weightless.
MIND can not be touched.
MIND is software. |

Results

Education becomes effective use of different ways in a classroom to promote collaborative learning with peer friendship to engage the learning process. Education is very important for all children's give all types of facilities students become more encourage with educational process with the help of teaching process through teachers. Teachers becomes a role play as a facilitator to engage students to choose better carrier choose with the help of education. So, Education is very crucial play role in every individual life.

Note: Images are used by internet sources as courtesy.

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